

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Building Resilient Education Systems: Evidence from Large-Scale Randomized Trials in Five Countries"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Anirudh Tagat

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Building Resilient Education Systems: Evidence from Large-Scale Randomized Trials in Five Countries"[\[1\]](#). To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Anonymous evaluation 1](#)
2. [Anonymous evaluation 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	90	4.3
Evaluator 2	83	3.9

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries**Anonymous evaluator 1**

The paper studies an important question [surrounding the] effectiveness of low-cost education programs which could reduce learning losses faced by primary [school] students due to shocks or emergencies in five developing countries.

Anonymous evaluator 2

Provides important evidence on [the] effectiveness of a low-tech intervention to stem learning losses from school closures (likely to increase in coming years) by scaling it up vertically & across diverse geographies

Note that [the] results only apply to numeracy skills and for temporary and abrupt school closures. Future work should see if it is effective for other skills & circumstances (displaced people, girls), and if contextualizing content/methods improves outcomes.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁴	90	(85, 95)	5	83	(73, 93)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁶				80	(72, 88)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	95	(90, 100)	8	88	(78, 98)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁹	85	(80, 90)	10	78	(68, 88)
Logic & communication ¹¹	84	(75, 90)	12	79	(71, 87)

Open, collaborative, replicable ¹³	75 ¹⁴	(60, 90)	¹⁵	62	(52, 72)
Real-world relevance ^{16,17}	95	(90, 100)	¹⁸	90	(85, 95)
Relevance to global priorities ^{19, 20}	95	(90, 100)	²¹	90	(85, 95)

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.3	(3.7, 4.8)	²²	3.9	(3.5, 4.4)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.5	(4.0, 4.8)	²³	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Evaluation manager's discussion

We sought two evaluations of this well-regarded paper, which has since received the 2024 [ADB-IEA Innovative Policy Research Award](#). This paper provides evidence on remote instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors conducted several powered RCTs in India, Kenya, Nepal, The Philippines, and Uganda. They find that delivering tutorials over the phone can stem learning loss. The authors also provide valuable evidence on the *setting* within which remote teaching/learning may be most effective; they find no major difference between NGO-provided tutorials and government-provided ones (if anything, the latter do better, assuaging fears about scalability within government systems).²⁴ (The 'null effect' is not tight. The point estimates for the government-provided tutorials is substantially larger than for NGOs (0.315 SDs vs 0.263 SDs) with standard errors of about 0.05 SDs for each, suggesting fairly wide confidence intervals for each.)²⁵

The two evaluators were asked specifically to comment on the design of the RCTs, the claims, and the policy considerations arising from the paper.

Evaluator 1 mentions that more details are needed on the design of the phone tutorials to be able to fully understand the impacts it might have, and to understand whether the efficacy of the tutorials might be undermined by shared phone ownership or similar constraints that low-income households in developing countries typically operate in. They also suggested a closer look at channels (explanations for the results obtained) related to health (given the pandemic) and via greater attention from caregivers. The authors would do well to consider these.

The second evaluation provides a more detailed and careful look at the claims as well as the policy implications. They make specific suggestions for authors to provide more details of the SMS-only intervention (again, likely helpful for scaling or translating this evidence into other contexts), as well as some contextual factors related to the delivery of the intervention. They also mention several issues related to the *scaling* of this intervention.

A key consideration here: if many individuals in a household are sharing a phone this could impede efficient delivery. If this was the case for a majority of households in this trial, this could be seen as an underestimate of the impact of an intervention in a context where everyone had (or was provided with) their own phone.

Overall, the paper makes a valuable contribution to our understanding of how to scale education interventions in emergency settings, especially in low-resource contexts.

References

1. Angrist, N., Ainomugisha, M., Bathena, S. P., Bergman, P., Crossley, C., Cullen, C., Letsomo, T., Matsheng, M., Panti, R. M., Sabarwal, S., & Sullivan, T., et al. (2023). Building Resilient Education Systems: Evidence

from Large-Scale Randomized Trials in Five Countries. NBER Working Paper No. 31208.
<https://doi.org/10.3386/w31208>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. The quality of the paper is very high. The contribution of the project, the credibility of the methods used to study causality, its impact on real world issues. Furthermore, the cost effectiveness nature of the intervention makes it very useful. [↵](#)
6. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

8. Please see my comments above. [↵](#)
9. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

10. Overall, I liked the simplicity of the RCT design and it was cleanly executed. The main results are presented in an interesting manner. My concerns are with the robustness checks and mechanisms. I have pointed out the same above. ↵

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ↵

12. The logical flow in the data analysis is consistent with the arguments set forth by the authors. There is some repetition of content in Sections III B and C (already covered in the Introduction) which can be avoided. ↵

13.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

↵

14. Manager's note: This evaluators' response (in the comment) suggests that they may have been interpreting this criteria differently than we intended. ↵

15.

Replicability in a RCT is always a tricky point. The RCT seems to be a costly matter however the intervention is very cost-effective. Plus the authors were able to reduce the costs further from the Botswana study due to economies of scale. From a perspective of cost, I would say the RCT is not very replicable. However, with reference to discussion on methods and data analysis, the authors have done a good job. The tables and figures are labelled properly and explained well. They are easily replicable.

Managers' note: This does not fully capture our intentions when we asked about replicability (and openness, and data sharing). We did not want this to consider the costs of running a new RCT, which is largely out of the researchers' control. We will work on explaining this criteria better in future.

↵

16.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

↵

17.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

18. Yes, the research question being of utmost importance and relevant to deal with the education crisis, I would say the paper and the suggested intervention could be relevant to practitioners. [↵](#)

19. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

20.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

21. The paper deals with a global priority: learning loss due to emergencies. The intervention of using phone tutorials with SMS reminders is a cost-effective method which could have high impact on primary education learning in developing countries. [↵](#)

22. The paper studies an important question of effectiveness of low cost education programs which could reduce learning losses faced by primary students due to shocks or emergencies in 5 developing countries. Given the nature of the question and the effectiveness of the intervention, I think it should be placed in a top tier journal. [↵](#)

23. In continuation with my previous point, the importance of the question makes it one of the recent interesting topics in economics research. Additionally, since the low cost intervention has effectively been scaled across 5 countries, I think the study has made a unique contribution by contributing to the external validity of education in emergencies research. [↵](#)

24. Footnote: In previous related contexts, when programs were passed from NGO trials to government implementation, the program effectiveness waned. [↪](#)

25. Government Teachers: The impact of phone calls and SMS messages delivered by government teachers was a 0.314 standard deviation improvement in learning. Based on a simple normal approximation, the 80% CI for this effect is (0.248, 0.380). NGO Teacher Aides: The impact of phone calls and SMS messages delivered by NGO teacher aides was a 0.263 standard deviation improvement in learning. Again a normal distribution suggests an 80% CI for this effect of (0.206, 0.320). [↪](#)

References

1. Angrist, N., Ainomugisha, M., Bathena, S. P., Bergman, P., Crossley, C., Cullen, C., ... Sullivan, T. (2023). *Building Resilient Education Systems: Evidence from Large-Scale Randomized Trials in Five Countries*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31208> [↪](#)